

Nwulite Obodo Open Data License (NOODL)

SUMMARY SHEET

Summary of Licence Conditions

Term	Recipients in Africa/ Developing Countries		Recipients outside these regions	
		✓		✓
Use & share	Worldwide & royalty-free	✓	With paybacks	✓
Adapt/remix	Yes	✓	Yes	✓
Commercial use	Inside developing countries; outside <i>with benefit-sharing</i>	✓	Permitted with royalties/benefits	✓
Share-Alike	Required	✓	Required	✓
Attribution	Yes	✓	Yes	✓
No additional restrictions	Yes	✓	Yes	✓

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www.licensingafricandatasets.com

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